

FOREST4EU partner: GIS
 OG: Di-Gozd
 OG's country: Slovenia
 Type of Innovation: Service

Di-Gozd Digital Forest Inventory-Internet app

Introduction

The online application allows users to review their own forest land based on existing public data and estimate the value of their own forest's annual yield. Users can also assess the condition, value, and control measures of the forest based on their own images created with the mobile application. The application provides users with analysis tools for reviewing the images created, a method for calculating the value of trees, and a system for monitoring events on the forest plot.

Lessons learned

From the online application, we can get an overview of our own plots using publicly available data. It provides us with control over the interventions carried out and an overview of the records created. It allows us to make a more accurate assessment of the condition of the forest plot. It gives us information about our planned harvest and value.

Figure 1: Overview of digital platform.

For further information contact

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The information presented in this factsheet was developed by the FOREST4EU partner, drawing on the innovations and knowledge generated by the indicated operational group with their explicit authorization.

Further information

<https://di-gozd.si/>

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